

CMS lines for shallow rainfed lowland situation

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We are working to develop parental lines for hybrid rice for the rainfed lowland ecosystem in eastern India. Although hundreds of cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines have been developed for breeding hybrids for the irrigated ecosystem in India, hardly any have been reported so far for the rainfed lowlands.

We therefore converted 13 popular lowland cultivars into CMS lines through repeated backcrossing with three male sterility sources: wild abortive, Kalinga-I, and *O. perennis*. These sources, in BC₆ generation, were grown in the field along with their maintainers during the 1994 wet season. We recorded pollen sterility, spikelet fertility in bagged panicles, plant height, days to 50% flowering, and panicle exertion for each of the CMS and maintainer lines.

All 13 CMS lines were completely pollen sterile with white anthers and did not set any seed in bagged panicles (see table). Moti A, Kalashree A, and Padmini A were late-duration varieties while the rest were medium-duration.

The CMS lines are semidwarf to semitall in stature, with stiff straw. All were shorter (1-56 cm) than their respective isonuclear

Agronomic characters of CMS lines and their maintainers developed at CRRI, Cuttack, Orissa, India. 1994 wet season.

CMS ^a or maintainer lines	Pedigree of A lines	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet fertility (%)	Plant height (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Panicle exertion (%)
Moti A	V20A/Moti (WA)	100	0	90	127	73.1
Moti B	-	-	87.9	120	124	100
Kalashree A	V20A/Kalashree (WA)	100	0	95	134	68.7
Kalashree B	-	-	82.9	113	130	100
Padmini A	V20A/Padmini (WA)	100	0	119	119	80.3
Padmini B	-	-	89.5	145	118	100
IET11350 A	V20A/IET11350 (WA)	100	0	95	97	80.4
IET11350 B	-	-	82.5	100	95	100
IET10428 A	V20A/IET10428 (WA)	100	0	104	98	79.3
IET10428 B	-	-	90.0	105	90	100
IET11668 A	V20A/IET11668 (WA)	100	0	93	96	81.3
IET11668 B	-	-	74.4	102	95	100
BKS64 A	V20A/BKS 64 (WA)	100	0	85	94	77.8
BKS64 B	-	-	86.7	99	95	100
Manipur A	Annada A/Manipur (WA)	100	0	82	100	67.3
Manipur B	-	-	82.5	92	99	100
Mirai A	Krishna A/Mirai (Kalinga-I)	100	0	79	100	70.1
Mirai B	-	-	80.6	88	99	100
Blazin A	Krishna A/Blazin (Kalinga-I)	100	0	70	95	66.1
Blazin B	-	-	74.8	126	102	100
IET10983-I A	IR62829A/IET10983 (WA)	100	0	75	100	66.6
IET10983 B	-	-	80.4	82	97	100
IET10983-II	IR66707 A/IET10983 (<i>O. perennis</i>)	100	0	65	98	62.3
IET10983 B	-	-	81.5	85	97	100
Tharrangsong A	IR66707 A/Tharrangsong (<i>O. perennis</i>)	100	0	71	88	69.3
Tharrangsong B	-	-	78.7	75	85	100

^aCMS lines are in the BC₆ generation.

maintainers. Their plant heights and durations are considered ideal for use in devel-

oping hybrids for the shallow rainfed lowland situation in India.

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Majhera 7, a direct seeded rainfed upland spring rice for Uttar Pradesh, India

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Spring rice is a major rainfed crop in the uplands of Uttar Pradesh, India. It is direct dry seeded from mid-March to mid-April and harvested in September-October. Only two spring rice varieties had been released to date: Majhera 3 in the early 1960s and VL 206 in 1983. Varieties grown in this

region must have long duration and drought tolerance, especially during May and June.

To address this need, we developed Majhera 7 from germplasm collected from the Kumaun uplands. After numerous trials (Table 1), Majhera 7 was recommended for release as a commercial variety in the Uttar Pradesh hill zone under direct dry seeded rainfed upland conditions.

In agronomical evaluation trials involving different sowing dates and fertilizer doses, Majhera 7 yielded more than checks Majhera 3 and VL 206. Maximum yield for the variety was obtained using a 7 Apr sowing date. Majhera 7 yielded 23.9% more than Majhera 3 and 6.3% more than

VL 206 when 75 kg N and 11 kg P ha⁻¹ were applied.

Majhera 7 matures in 174-187 d and fits well in common crop rotations: spring rice - wheat - ragi - toria - fallow and spring rice - wheat - barnyard millet - barley. It is 95-105 cm tall, erect, and with broad, dark-green leaves. It has medium-bold grain, a length-breadth ratio of 2.24, and a 21 g thousand-grain weight. Milling recovery is 80%. Majhera 7 is widely adaptable and shows field resistance to stem borer, leaf folder, grasshopper, sucking insects, and blast. (See Table 2 for morpho-agronomic characters of Majhera 7, Majhera 3, and VL 206.) ■